

**UNIMOBILE: ENHANCING UNIVERSIDAD DE MANILA STUDENT
EXPERIENCE THROUGH A SMART MOBILE PORTAL APPLICATION****Ronald Fernandez**

Professor, College of Computing Studies, Universidad de Manila, Philippines

John Miko Garcia

UG Students, College of Computing Studies, Universidad de Manila, Philippines

Kier Merza

UG Students, College of Computing Studies, Universidad de Manila, Philippines

Eula Jay Dela Cruz

UG Students, College of Computing Studies, Universidad de Manila, Philippines

Jerrymie Arceo

UG Students, College of Computing Studies, Universidad de Manila, Philippines

ABSTRACT

The application aims to improve school communication and improve the process by offering real-time grade viewing, subject schedules, faculty evaluation, announcements, chatrooms, and an event calendar all on a single mobile platform. The primary goal is to provide a solution that satisfies the needs of the university community, especially students who rely heavily on mobile devices. The Agile methodology and a developmental design were employed in the study. To find issues with the current portal, information was gathered via surveys, interviews, and observations. Flutter and Firebase were used in the development of the system, which was frequently tested for functionality, dependability, usability, integration, performance, and user acceptance testing. According to gathered results, UniMobile addresses problems with poor mobile accessibility, restricted communication, and information flow delays. User feedback verified that the prototype provides better organization, quicker navigation, and enhanced communication between administrators, teachers, and students. The findings demonstrate how a mobile portal promotes a more welcoming learning environment. UniMobile reduces misunderstandings, speeds up the delivery of updates, and helps students better handle their information. Faster communication and easier information sharing also benefit administrators and faculty. UniMobile enhances the UDM portal's usability and accessibility. The app solves the shortcomings of the current system and meets the expanding digital demands of the university community by offering a solution.

Keywords:

UniMobile, student portal, mobile application, academic services, communication, Universidad de Manila

INTRODUCTION

Technology is a huge component in making things faster, easier, and more useful these days. Digital platforms enable students and school workers do their homework and other chores. Universidad de Manila (UDM) already has a student portal, but it has certain issues, such as being slow and not having many ways to contact people or keep track of grades. These issues lead to a lot of delays and frustration for both students and staff. They can now enjoy a system that works better and is easier to use, which saves time and effort. The primary objective of this study is to update the UDM portal by converting it into a mobile application that is available at all times and in all locations. It does this by making communication better, making it easier to get to academic records, streamlining the processes for getting cleared and enrolling, and making the learning environment more open and organized. The researchers focused on these three goals to guide the study: (1) to find out what features and changes were needed based on feedback from students, faculty, and staff; (2) to test the app's usability and accessibility; and (3) to find out which communication channels should be given the most attention in the

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research Management (IJETRM)

<https://ijetrm.com/>

system. Finally, to be clear, this study defines important terms like Academic Records (school-related documents like grades and schedules), Enrollment Status (a student's official registration in a semester), Faculty Management (tools for teachers to view schedules and student lists), and the technologies used like Android Studio and Flutter, which make the app work well and be easy to use. In summary, UniMobile wants to develop a smarter and more modern academic site that will help everyone at UDM.

OBJECTIVES

The main goal of this project is to transform the Universidad de Manila community into a mobile application that gives easy access to school services. It aims to improve the usual way of university communication and make it more productive and informative for students, professors, and administrators. The UDM mobile app provides features such as school announcements, subjects and schedules, grade viewing, faculty evaluation, chatrooms, and real-time updates about the school, including events and activities. Instead of visiting multiple websites, portals, or offices, the proposed system can be accessed anytime and anywhere, which makes it more convenient and time-saving for the university community.

In this study, the objectives are centered on analyzing the features of the app and the opinions of students, faculty, and administrators about the current portal. The researchers aim to know what users like, dislike, or want to improve through survey questionnaires, and then identify which features need to be added, changed, or removed. Another objective is to find out the challenges students have faced in using the existing portal, especially in checking grades, schedules, and other services. The study also looks into how mobile-based messaging, announcements, and event notifications can change the way students communicate with university departments compared to the current system. It also aims to measure the effect of UniMobile on student engagement by looking at their experiences with both academic functions, like grades and schedules, and administrative functions. Lastly, the research evaluates the usability and accessibility of UniMobile through user testing and feedback, focusing on how easy it is to navigate the app, how clear the content is, and how responsive the app is when used across different devices.

METHODOLOGY

Developing the Universidad de Manila (UDM) Mobile App is a step-by-step procedure guaranteeing it satisfies the requirements of staff, teachers, and students. Agile methodology will be used on developing the mobile application. It uses the Agile Model in Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC), that makes sure that the mobile application develops continuously for every stage and requires user feedback for further improvements. Agile methodology is flexible that helps Unimobile grow and evolve. The experimentation we can conduct, the data we collect, and the recommendations we are able to refine create a more intelligent and engaging experience for the user.

Figure 1 Agile Model

IJETRM

**International Journal of Engineering Technology Research Management
(IJETRM)**

<https://ijetrm.com/>

Planning

It is the initial phase at this time, the team collects data about the most crucial characteristics professors and students require. It aims to understand the needs of students, teachers, and staff. This phase involved collecting data on existing systems, conducting interviews and surveys with future users, and identifying essential features and functions.

Design

This phase follows this one developer build a straightforward, user-friendly interface ensuring the app is simple to use. It focuses on creating a user-friendly and intuitive interface through wireframing and UI/UX design, ensuring accessibility and ease of navigation, and obtaining design approval from users.

Develop

This phase starts once the design is set it uses tools like Flutter or React Native to construct the app so it runs well on Android devices. The functional app was built using modern tools for cross-platform compatibility, with features implemented based on user needs.

Test

This phase instructors and students use it to identify problems requiring correction. The app is formally launched and made available for download after all runs well. Beta testing was conducted with selected students and faculty to identify and resolve bugs or usability issues through feedback and iterative debugging, along with functional and performance testing.

Release

This phase involved launching the app on the Play Store, informing the university community, and offering installation support and initial training if necessary.

Feedback

After a certain time after the deployment of the application, reviews from the user will be compiled and be gathered for insights on what are their opinions on the application and ideas to add.

Figure 2 Conceptual Framework

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research Management (IJETRM)

<https://ijetrm.com/>

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section summarizes and discusses the evaluation results obtained from the ISO/IEC 25010-based questionnaire distributed to chosen respondents mostly for the student and faculty. The study focused on the Unimobile app for Universidad De Manila application's major quality features, such as functional suitability, performance efficiency, interaction capability, reliability, security, flexibility and safety. Each sub-criterion was scored on a five-point Likert scale, allowing users to identify both strengths and weaknesses based on their perceptions and interactions with the system.

Department/Role

The respondent focuses on students, professors who will usually interacts with the system from time to time and it professionals who will evaluate the system. Majority of the respondent are student tallying 57%, while proffesors are 32%, and IT professionals 11%. Having the respondent evaluate the system allows the proponents on how clear the system is and what are things to be considered for future enhancement.

Figure 3 Pie Chart for Department/Role

Functional Suitability

The Functional Suitability category received consistently high ratings, averaging above 4.4. Respondents particularly value the overall functions of the system, showing that the system effectively provides relevant features and tasks that is relevant in the university portal. Ensuring good function experience for the user by having accurate records and features.

Figure 4 Bar Graph for Functionality

Performance Efficiency

The Performance Efficiency scored strongly, with most sub-criteria averaging around 4.2. Responsiveness and Response Time received the highest marks, indicating that the system features load quickly. Network/Data Consumption also performed well, meaning the application does not consume too much data when in use and the app runs smoothly.

Figure 5 Bar Graph for Performance Efficiency

Interaction Capability

The Interaction Capability category with an average of 4.4 means the interaction between the user and the system is clear and concise, ensuring logos, icons and navigation menus would be easier for user to understand, also the user doesn't encounter too many errors in using the application.

Figure 6 Bar Graph for Usability

Reliability

The reliability category with an average of 4.6. It has the highest mark, which means the user can still navigate or access the app even in critical condition without errors, ensuring consistent university records.

Figure 7 Bar Graph for Reliability

Security

The system achieved an average mean score of 4.13 (Good) regarding security. Respondents agreed that the application adequately protects personal data, provides privacy control, and ensures account safety.

Figure 8 Bar Graph for Security

Flexibility

The flexibility category with an average of 4.5. The user evaluates on how easy it is to install the app without the need for assistance, also ensuring that navigating the app wouldn't require data loss and its adaptable to use even when its peak time. The Unimobile app is flexible to any challenges that the system may come across.

Figure 9 Bar Graph for Flexibility

Safety

The safety category with an average of 4.5 have the high marks because it ensures to protect the user from unauthorized access ensuring data integrity and safe communication between faculty and student. Protecting the user in any potential harm like account deletion or modification.

Figure 10 Bar Graph for Safety

User Evaluation Survey Summary

Overall, the UniMobile app got good feedback from the respondents across all the categories. Functional suitability and reliability received the highest scores, which means the users are satisfied with how the system works and how stable it is when being used. Flexibility and safety also received high ratings, showing that the app is easy to install, safe to use, and can protect user information properly. Performance efficiency and interaction capability were also rated positively, meaning the app runs smoothly, responds fast, and is easy for students and faculty to navigate. Security had the lowest score compared to the others, but still showed a good rating, which means there is still space for improvement in protecting accounts and privacy.

Criteria	Average Mean	Interpretation
Functional Sustainability	4.4	Strongly Agree
Performance Efficiency	4.2	Strongly Agree
Interaction Capability	4.4	Strongly Agree
Reliability	4.6	Strongly Agree
Security	4.13	Agree
Flexibility	4.5	Strongly Agree
Safety	4.5	Strongly Agree

Table I. User Evaluation Survey Summary

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to our project adviser for the continuous guidance, support, and encouragement given to us while we were doing this study. We also want to thank our panel members for their helpful comments and suggestions that really improved the quality of our work. We extend our appreciation to the students, professors, and staff of Universidad de Manila who took part in answering our surveys and interviews, because their cooperation and honest feedback were a big help in developing the UniMobile application. We are also thankful to our classmates and friends who supported us all throughout the process. We want to give thanks to our families for their patience, love, and inspiration during the making of this project. Above all, we give our deepest gratitude to God for giving us the strength, wisdom, and guidance to finish this study.

CONCLUSION

The UniMobile application was developed to improve the current UDM portal by making it more accessible and easier to use on mobile devices. Based on the results, the app was able to meet most of the needs of students, professors, and IT professionals. It improved communication, allowed faster access to grades and schedules, and created a more organized way of handling academic information. The high ratings in areas like functionality, reliability, flexibility, and safety show that the system is working well and can be trusted by users. Although security got the lowest rating among the categories, it still scored good which means the app is already effective but can still be improved further.

REFERENCES

- [1] Mac Iver, M. A., Wills, K., Sheldon, S., Clark, E., & Mac Iver, D. J. (2021). Urban parents at the portal: Family use of web-based information on ninth grade student course grades. *School Community Journal*, 31(1), 85–108. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1305386.pdf>
- [2] Grepon, B., Baran, N., Gumonan, K., Martinez, A., & Lacs, M. (in press). Designing and implementing e-schools system: An information systems approach to school management of a community college in northern Mindanao, Philippines. *International Journal of Computing Sciences Research*, in press. Doi: 10.25147/ijcsr.2017.001.1.74
- [3] Al-Ghamdi, F. M., AlHarthi, H., & AlShammari, N. (2021). A new model for enhancing student portal usage in Saudi Arabia universities. *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*. <https://etasr.com/index.php/ETASR/article/view/4132/2508>
- [4] Pardamean, B., Suparyanto, T., Cenggoro, T. W., Sudigyo, D., & Anugrahana, A. (2022). AI-based learning style prediction in online learning for primary education. *IEEE Access*, 10, 35725–35735. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9737111>
- [5] Ali, A., & Yong, E. S. (2021). The effect of using a learning portal in the subject of design and technology. *Kesan Penggunaan Portal Pembelajaran Dalam Subjek Reka Bentuk Dan Teknologi. Research and Innovation in Technical and Vocational Education and Training (RITVET)*, 1(2), Article 014. <https://publisher.uthm.edu.my/periodicals/index.php/ritvet/article/view/2135/1050>